

Review Article

Interest Group and Foreign Policy Decisions: A Brief Review of the Jewish Lobby Group and the United States Middle East Foreign Policy

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Abstract

Interest group plays critical role in foreign policy decisions. Opinion, perspective and position of interest group are major input parameters in foreign policy design and implementations. The Jewish lobby group is a loosed coalition of individual and group whose primary interest is the advancement of US Israel relations and the protection of the state of Israel. The lobby group over the years has become a major domestic determinant of the US Middle East foreign policy. Through the adoption of various strategies ranging from political campaign finance, bloc voting systems, lobbying, influence on the mass media and motion picture (Hollywood), frequent charges of anti-semitism, the Jewish lobby group shaped the US Middle East foreign policy making it entirely pro-Israel. Elite theories which offer scientific explanation for the dominance of minority elite over the masses provide theoretical foundation for the study. Secondary source of data collection was adopted to obtain fact relevant to the study. We concluded that based on the unrivalled effectiveness of the Jewish lobby group in shaping the United States Middle East foreign policy and other domestic affairs, interest groups are critical factor in foreign policy decision making processes.

Keywords: Lobby, Foreign Policy, Interest Group, Campaign Finance, Bloc-Voting, Anti-Semitism.

1. Introduction

Interest groups are major domestic determinant of foreign policies. Aside foreign policy, they also play pivotal roles in domestic policy decisions. In other word, opinion, position, demand and suggestion canvassed by interest group provide critical input parameters for foreign policy formulation and implementation. Interest groups are combination of individual with common share interest who tries to influence government for favorable policy output. When pockets of individual comes together to form a group with basic objective of influencing government decision in favour of its members, we refer to such group as interest group. Interest group in most cases are self-centered, their primary concern is the interest of their members and not that of the generality of the society. Although less frequent, some interest group allies with the other interest group to chant causes that are beneficial to the general interest of the society.

In every social political system, there are avalanches of interest group fighting for self-interest. In some settings, interest group are so powerful that they often held government by the Jugular therefore dictate the shape and direction of policy output to suit desired interest. This is the experience in the United State where group interest predominates on policy decisions. The US social political environment provides fertile ground for proliferation of interest group. The political system obviously is more receptive to group opinion and less recognition to individual position. In these circumstances, government policy mostly reflects the position of the dominant interest group. This practically explained the rationale behind the pro-Israel posture of the US Middle East foreign policy. The Jewish lobby group is a dominant interest group with huge financial muscle and unrivalled electoral power, they leverage these advantages to advance US-Israel relations and also shape the US Middle East foreign policy in a pro-Israel direction.

In Nigeria for instance, apart from the legally recognized association like the Nigerian Medical Association (NMA), Nigerian Bar Association (NBA), Nigeria Pharmaceutical Society, Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT), Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASSU), Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC), there are other group refers to as the "Cabal". They are faceless but very powerful and influential on government decisions. Fundamentally, interest groups in recent years have continued to play dominant role in shaping the

direction of government foreign relations. They determine types, nature of foreign and other diplomatic engagement. Major strategies adopted by interest group to influence government to achieve preferred policy output are lobbying, manipulation, maneuvering and campaign financing. Every foreign policy decisions emanate from the major arm of government especially the executive and the legislature. These arms of government are often the target of interest group, they lobby and manipulate the recruitment processes into the executive and the legislative arm of government to obtain policy output that favour their members and the cause represented.

The preponderance of interest group and the significant role plays in shaping the United States foreign policy decisions has become worrisome. Of critical concern is the ease with which the Jewish lobby an interest group manipulates and shapes the United States Middle East foreign policy making it entirely pro-Israel. The phenomenon is pervasive and persistence thus requires rigorous interrogation and intellectual dissection.

2. Review of Relevant Literature

There are divergent scholar's opinion on interest group and the significant roles they play in foreign policy and other domestic policy decisions. The scholars however concurred on the fact that interest groups are major determinant of foreign policies. According to Clive (2021) interest group also call special interest group, advocacy group or pressure group are any association of individual or organization, formally organize on the basis of one or more share concerns and they attempts to influence public policy to address those concerns. Clive went further to say that all interest group shared a desire to affect government policy to benefits themselves. In other word, interest groups are combination of individual who share common interest and they came together with the basic goal of influencing government policy to protect the interest. In the same vein, Hillegrass (2022), viewed interest group as an organization whose member share common concerns and they try to influence government policy affecting those concerns. He also viewed interest group as lobby group and described lobbying as one of the way interest group shape legislation and brings the view of their constituent to the attention of decision makers.

Baroni *et al.*, (2014), described interest group as organization which have political interest but do not seek political office. He further claimed that lobbying is a major instrument used by interest group to influence government policy. He sees lobbying as activity of political communication generally carried by interest group aimed at influencing policy output.

To Varaone and Eichenberger (2023), an interest group is an organization or a part of society which aim to defend the material interest of its members or promote the ideal cause of the group in the public space and to influence policy making. According the two scholars, interest group have basic characteristic which can be classified into the following:

- ✓ It is comprises of members which may be individual or collective group of actors.
- ✓ It is a structured organization who can take up different legal forms.
- ✓ They seek to influence public policy formation, the draft of legislation and implementation using various advocacy strategies to gain access to policy makers and institutional venue.
- ✓ Interest group does not seek to hold elected offices. They are private group that fight for a common cause using available strategies.

The foregoing expands frontier of knowledge on definition, classification, objectives as well as composition of interest group. It also revealed to a large extend the primary goal of interest group in any political system. Interest group are formed essentially not to seek political office but to influence government policy in favour of their members. In a similar vein, Lapalombra (1964), quoting from the encyclopedia.com 2018, sees interest group as group of voluntary individual who bonded themselves together for the defense of an interest. It is a conscious desire to have public policy or the authoritative allocation of value move in a particular general or specific direction. The underlying consideration of an interest group is the advancement of the interest of members. In specific circumstances, interest group fight for the general interest of the society especially those causes closely related to the peoples welfare. They could allies with other interest group to pressure government for general welfares based policy output but this does not form basic interest or primary objectives.

Yoho (1998), viewed interest group as organization who are private in nature, they attempted to influence public policy and they are not political parties and do not nominate candidate for public offices. In other word, interest groups are private organization, even though they influence government decision, they do not

seek to participate actively in politics by contesting for elected offices. The primary interest is to influence government policy to allies with the cause represented. Halpin and Nownes (2020), put together different definition of interest group and summarized the definition this way: “an interest group is any organization that attempts to affect government decisions. Using the United States as a sample, they opined further that the very broad definition is expansive enough to include the various types of organizations that interface with government in the United States. These types of organization include business firms, charities, churches, citizen group, labour union, political action committee (PAC), professional associations and others. From the preceding general analysis, an interest group is deemed to possess the following specific characteristics which distinguished it from other loose coalition group.

- ✓ It is an association of individual or groups.
- ✓ The individual or group composition share common concerns.
- ✓ They try to influence government policy using various strategies mostly lobbying to address those concerns.
- ✓ They do not seek elected offices, they are private in nature but exert significant influence on public policies specifically those that affect the cause the group represented.

2.1. Foreign Policy Analysis

At this juncture, it is imperative to elucidate albeit briefly the concept of foreign policy, its basic determinants and how states fashion out foreign policy objectives. This provides an in-depth understanding and context within which we can establish the nexus between interest group and foreign policy decision making. In other word, the subject matter of this article is situated within the context of foreign policy thus, abridged analysis of foreign policy processes become very imperative.

It is generally a universal maxim that no country is an island of its own, countries must relate and communicate with each other’ in other to derive mutual benefit and gains from such relationship. The international environment provides opportunities for bi-lateral and multi-lateral cooperation among independent states. However, relationships in the international system are not carry out hap-hazardly or base on rule of thumb, there are clear cut policy and objectives that guild international interactions and relationships, these policies and objectives form the tenet of foreign policies.

There is no universally acceptable definition of foreign policy. Some scholars offered opinion on what constitute foreign policy by putting forward various definitions. The definitions are viewed from different perspectives based on the orientation and background of each scholar. Put succinctly, according to Akpotor and Nwolise (2014) “due to lack of consensus on the meaning of foreign policy, it will be necessary to x-ray an avalanche of definitions which will not elude further evaluation”.

Interestingly, renowned and leading scholars in the field of international relations have in their works, provided helpful tips and useable clarifications on the concept. According to Adeniji (1968), “foreign policy is a projection of the country’s national interest into the trans-national arena, and the consequent interaction of one state with the other. Northedge (1968) sees foreign policy as “the use of political influence to induce other states to exercise their law-making power in a manner desired by the states concerned: it is an interaction between forces originating outside the country’s borders and those working within them”. To Frankel (1963) foreign policy consists of decisions and actions, which involve to an appreciable extent, relations between one state and others. Tyoden (1989), refers to foreign policy as measures consciously designed and put in place by a government for the attainment of specific goals and objectives in the international system. To Holsti, cited in Asogwa, (2009) it is the actions of a state towards the external environment and the conditions usually domestics under which these actions are formulated.

Morgenthau (1948), sees foreign policy as the struggle for the mind of men. Akindele (2013), on the other hand states that the foreign policy of any country is both a series of articulated demands on the internal system of a sovereign state and a series of response to external events and situation over which a country however powerful have no control over. Kolawole (2005) posited that foreign policy is the mirror for ascertaining the attitudes, feelings and behavior of state in relation with other states and non-state actors in the international arena. It aims at influencing the international system toward the attainment of what it perceived in consonance with its national interest. To Akinyemi (1974), foreign policy refers to aggregate of actions and non-actions by which a country regulates its relationship with the rest of the world. According to Oddih (2002), “the rules, decisions and guild lines that guild the relationship between one state and another is call foreign policy. Thus, foreign policy shows a course of action adopted by a state in relations with other states in the international system. Kissinger (1966), sees foreign policy as” the compass by which a given

state navigates her world through the storm of international politics. It is the summation of thoughts, actions and principles on external affairs taken by decision makers with the intention of achieving a large range of goals and short time objectives. The definitions of foreign policy are as many as the number of international relations scholars, we can continue with the definition by different scholars without end. We thus focused on few definitions that are popular and gaining wider recognition within the field of International relations.

Finally, Akpotor and Nwolise (2014), summarized the concept of foreign policy this way “it is the pattern of behaviors that one state adopts while pursuing its interest in relations with other states. It is concern with the process of making decisions to follow specific course of action in the international system.” A common denominator among the various definitions is that foreign policy is concern with behavior of states toward other states in the international system such behaviors are geared toward pursuance and achievement of national interest. For instance, the United States Middle East foreign policy is design to achieve specifics objective in the region, these objectives are in line with defined national interest.

2.2. Basic Determinants of Foreign Policy

States foreign policies decisions are premised on certain domestic, external factors, circumstances and developments, which could be referred to as variables. These variables shape the direction of foreign policies of states. According to Folarin (2017), foreign policy decision making are guided by certain fundamental considerations which constitute its determinants. The determinants provide a clear-cut direction on foreign policy decisions. In other word, there are basic factors that determine foreign policy formulation and implementations processes. Such determinants could be broken into external and domestic factors. However, for the purpose of this study, we will briefly highlight the determinants and detail analysis on few because such discourse is outside the purview of the study but rather provide background for proper understanding of the subject matter. Some of the determinants among others are geographic-strategic factors, economic potential and viability of a state, structure of government, internal processes, military capabilities, pressure or interest group, public opinion and leadership etc. Looking at military capability for instance, the ability of United States to successfully pursue and prosecute its foreign policy all over the world especially in the Middle East is due to her military capabilities.

With the collapse of former Soviet Union, United States emerged as the world super power with the strongest military capabilities. In other word, the world order became unipolar with the demise of the USSR and the United States at the tip of the pyramid. Strategic action such as liberation of Kuwait, military operation in Afghanistan and subsequent killing of Osama-Bin-Laden in Pakistan, dethronement of Saddam Hussein of Iraq on accusation of possession of Weapon of Mass Destruction (WMD) and even instigation of internal unrest that led to the dismantling of Muammar Gaddafi’s government in Libya are as a result of United States military capability. It will be suicidal for countries like Nigeria with less powerful military capability to pursue such deadly foreign policy. This account for why most African countries like Nigeria prefer peaceful relation with neighboring countries and other countries in the international arena.

Similarly, strong, virile public opinion and pressure group to a large extent determine the direction of a country foreign policy. In fact, public opinion and pressure group represent major domestic determinant of foreign policy. In Nigeria for instance, pressure group such as Nigerian Bar Association, Nigeria Labor Congress, and Nigerian Medical Association etc. plays significant role in determining the direction of the country’s foreign policy. There are instances where foreign policy decisions were cancelled due to strong opposition from pressure group. The Nigerian Anglo-Defense Agreement with the British government was abrogated in 1962 due to opposition from pressure groups and popular rejection by public opinion. A critical element of foreign policy is national interest and power. The two elements are intricately interwoven and inseparable in international politics. The national interest answers the question of what a state desire to achieve in the international system. Power provides veritable means to pursue and achieve national interest objectives. According to Efebeh (2020), “the foreign policy of any state in the international system is drawn around the national interest. However, the concept of national interest is the most controversial in contemporary international relations. It represent varieties of desire pursued by various states in their interactions with other states in the international system and cannot be pinned down to specifics.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. The Group Theory

The theory that best provide theoretical foundation for this article is the group theory. Group theory is primarily concerns with the examination of how individual actors assemble to form political groups that participate in the political processes and influence government decisions. In every political systems group

constantly struggle and compete for power and their interaction and exchange result in governmental procedures, structures and policy output. In other word, the group approaches to politics examine the significant role that people hold in the political system as well as the relationship between the action of collective group and its impact on the political socialization and behavior. Succinctly put, the group approach is premised on the belief that political activity involves more than just one individual, political activity occurs instead through individual actors coming together in a particular group setting.

The theory contended that neither individuals nor whole societies are significant political actors but the actions of groups in pursuit of their various interests are the sources of policy and the substance of politics and that public policy is the product of group struggle from the organized masses. Such public policy directly reflects significantly the interest of the dominant group. In other word, in every society, there are several groups jostling for and competing to influence government decisions in their favour. More often than not, political decision reflects the interest of group with better strategies and influences.

Group approach to politics was mostly associated with Bentley (1908) who is regarded as the progenitor of the school of thought. Subsequently, Truman (1981), later took up Bentley's empirical approach to study the activities of group behavior and its impact on the political processes. Bentley main contribution to the analysis of political thought was his group theory. He posited that the traditional distinctions in political science between democratic and dictatorial systems of government were largely superficial. He argued that "all political systems really consisted of several separate groups competing with one another for influence over policy decision. The role of the government was essentially that of political broker, responding to the demands and influence of the different groups and distributing resources in form of policies in response". In political analysis, group theory postulated that an inquiry into the political behavior and phenomenon should be sought from the interactions and relationships between groups as they compete with each other for the values of the society.

Bentley averred further that societies consists of a large number of social, political, ethnic or economic groups, more or less well-organized in political competition with each other to put pressure on the government into producing the policies favorable to the relevant groups. Each group's members were united by their shared preferences on specific policies, and the preferences are usually revealed by the members' activity or behavior." The fundamentals of group theory hold that the interaction of groups is the basis of political life without group there will be no orderly political life. In the opinion of Truman, group activity determined legislation, administration and adjudication. In his words, "institutions do not provide the best framework for explaining how society functions. He argued that politics is a group affair and each group is competing against each other for power. He also added that group theory helps one to understand the pattern of process involving mass of activities and not a collection of individuals.

In a similar development, Okereke (2015), argued that "group emerges from frequent interaction among its individual members which is directed by their share interest, it provides the best framework for understanding how political parties and other association of group's functions to promote and protect their interest. To Ikenga (2018), groups are comparable to elite in any social political system, they are small numerically but influential, the influence affords them ability to shape government policies. Generally, group theory sees politics as a group affair and each group is competing against each other for power, output from the political systems reflects the interest of the dominant group". The group theories fundamentally see interactions of groups as the basis of political life and rejected statist abstractive position and that group activities determine legislation, execution and adjudications which are the basic function of government.

The theory has however been criticized for placing too much emphasize on group and relegating the importance of individual as a component of a group. The critics argue that group is made up of collection of individuals and that in-depth understanding of group behavior presupposes a deep dive inquiry into the characteristic and behavioral pattern of the individual that make up the group. Aggregation of behavior of individual within the group provides deep understanding of the group behavior and could inferably enable near accurate prediction of the general group behavioral orientation.

The theory draw relevancy to the subject matter of this study to the extent that the Jewish lobby group which is the focal point of the study is an interest group, their basic interest is the protection of the state of Israel. It is a loosed coalition of individual and group seeking to influence the United States government for policy concession in line with their interest. The group deployed strategies ranging from campaign donation, bloc voting, lobbying, influence on Think Thank group, grooming student campus activism, charges of anti-

semitism to influence the US Middle East policy. There are several interest group in the United States however, the US Middle East foreign policy reflect the interest of the Jewish lobby group because the Jewish lobby group is the dominant and more powerful group in the country.

4. Interest Group in the United States

United States society is renowned for proliferation of interest group, there are thousands of interest group in the US political data base, each represent specific interest and they seek to influence the government for policy concession. The interest group range from Abortion and Reproductive, Agriculture and Food Processing, Animals and Wildlife Arts, Entertainment, and History, Businesses and Consumers, Campaign Finance and Elections, Civil Liberty, Employment, Affirmative Actions, and Civil Rights, Conservative, Crime, Defense, Drug, Economic and Fiscal, Education, Energy, Oil and Natural Resources, Finance and Banking, Foreign Affairs and Foreign Aid, Guns, Housing and Property, Health and Health Care to Immigration, just to mention few. Each categorization of interest group share common interest and they seek to influence the United States government to protect the shared interest. For instance the National Raffle Association goal is to promote and encourage Raffle shooting on scientific basis and also protection of members against subversive government policies. J Street is the political abode for pro-Israel Americans they broaden debate around Israel and the Middle East in national politics and within the American Jewish community. The Arab American Institute (AAI) is a nonprofit organization committed to the civic and political empowerment of Americans of Arab descent. We have endless list of interest group in the United States seeking to influence government policy to achieve desire objective and to protect the interest of members.

Arguing on the reason for the proliferation of interest group in the United states social political and economic systems Nehme (2021), asserted that the United States is a pluralistic and complex society, individual voice can hardly be heard except when such individual come together as group to fight for common cause. Nehme went further to say that, "in a pluralistic society like in the United States, organization, presentation and attainment of varied interest is dependent on the ability of the concerns group to manipulate the active principles of democracy". Nehme juxtapose his position by saying that "the United States society and government has become so large and complex to the point at which an individual citizen voter in an election of over 100 million has limited capacity or even motivation for making his or her voice heard" To Nehme, the major way to be heard in the United States is when you organize only virile and sound organization that have access to government apparatus. Organizations in the United States have lobby as their most efficient tools to achieve desire objectives. He concluded by asserting that "for those who know how to play the game of politics in the USA, the first thing that they do is the formation of organizations. These organizations assume different titles and names such as Think Tank group, evangelical group, association, political parties, interest groups and lobby group.

According to Thomas (2023), viewed in the context of political processes, interest groups are formed to attempt to influence the decision-making process of governments to achieve desire objectives. As a given fact, the understanding of American politics is based on the political organization (group) as a unit of analysis. In other words, to properly understand the United States political processes one must view it with the lens of group as the focus of analysis. Thus, analysis and understanding of group activities enriches knowledge of the operation and intricacies of the US political system. As a corollary to this, Thomas advocated for collective bargaining based on his understanding of the American society. The understanding here is that there is power in numbers, and political institutions are more likely to respond to a collective rather than to an individual voice.

The foregoing analysis underscores the rationale behind the Jews coming together to form strong and virile lobby organizations with the sole objective of utilizing access to government apparatus to manipulate United States Middle East foreign policies in favor of Israel. There is a general understanding that individual actions yield little or no result rather group action make significant impact on the US government. Succinctly put, government is likely to give attention to group demands than that made by individual. This belief may have undoubtedly underlined the proliferation of interest group in the United States all attempting to influence government policies to address their concerns. However, the ability of any of the interest group to achieve objectives as earlier stated is depended on will power, capacity and in addition, financial muscles.

5. The Jews in the United States Social Political System

It is imperative at this juncture to provide brief exposition on who is naturally and biologically a Jew and the ethno-religious group calls the Jews in the United States. This become very important since the primary focus of the article is on the Jewish lobby group. Such brief description will ultimately engender better

understanding of the subject matter and direction of the study. As stated in the Old Testament Bible, the Jews or Jewish people whichever way we look at it are ethno-religious group or nationalities who are said to have originated from Israel and Judah of the biblical period. Jewish ethnic, religious and nationhood are closely interwoven and interconnected. Krausz and Tulea (1997), defined a Jew as one who practices the Jewish religion of Judaism. They include both converts and those who have been members of the Jewish religion from birth. Thus, "a Jew is one, who is a descendant of the ancient Israelite group and therefore is a member of the Jewish race". From the above, it is clear that one can be a Jew in three distinct ways: through practicing Judaism, a religion historically identified with the Jewish race, one can also be a Jew through convert to the fold of Judaism and one regardless of current religious identity is directly a descendant of Jewish ancestor which traditionally applies to patrilineal and matrilineal descent, one whose father or mother is born as Jew. According to McGongle and Herman (2017), traditional Israel law of return stipulates that a Jew is someone with a Jewish mother or someone who has converted to Judaism and is not a member of other religions. This implies that one whose mother is a Jew or who through religious conversion is automatically a Jew. The encyclopedia Britannica give further description of who is a Jew. "A Jew in a broader sense of the term is any person belonging to the world-wide group that constitutes through descent or conversion a continuation of the ancient Jewish people, who were themselves descendant of the Hebrew of the Old Testament Bible.

From the above, we can understand clearly the classifications that underpin the distinctive characteristic of a Jew. The characteristics as identified above enable us to also delineate a Jew from other non-Jews who professed to be Jew but do not fall within the Jewish criteria of membership.

The Jews in the United States are referred to as American Jews. They are American citizen who are of Jewish descent either by birth, religious inclination, ethnicity, culture or nationality. Even though they are full-fledged United States citizen born and bred in the country or become citizen by other method of acquiring citizenship, by registration or naturalization, they do not totally extricate themselves from Israel which they consider as their ancestral home land. Identification with the state of Israel closely forms part of Jewish identity, social-cultural life and value systems. As stated earlier, the Jews before migrating to the United States were disintegrated and scattered all over Europe in such countries as Eastern Europe, Spain, Germany and Portugal, Russian, Poland where they live peacefully until compelled to emigrate by development in their host countries. According to Stevenson (2018) "impelled by economic hardship, persecution and the great social and political upheavals of the 9th century industrialization, over population and urbanizations, millions of Europe Jews left their town and villages and embarked on the arduous journey to the golden land of America" Similarly, on Jewish emigration to US, Zollman (2002) opined that "the Jews from Germany emigrated to the United States as a result of persecution and oppressive government policies borne out of hostile political environments. He argued further that "the Jews especially those from Germany, emigrated because of persecution, restrictive laws, economic hardship and the failure of movement widely supported by the German Jews advocating for reform there". The emigration to US was as a result persecution, discrimination and racial discrimination meted to the Jews in Europe. This ugly experience triggered the need to seek for greener pastures outside Europe. They desire conducive environment where their security and safety could be guaranteed, United States was thus considered preferable for settlement.

Succinctly put, when we talk about Jews in America, we refer to individual or group domicile in the United States but share connection with Israel which they regarded as their ancestral home through matrilineal or patrilineal descent and those who practice Judaism as a religion and do not belong to any other religion group. Judaism is a religion identified with the Jewish people, this commonly manifests in their mode of dressings and other social cultural life.

6. The Emergence of the Jewish Lobby Group in the United States

As stated earlier, the Jew as a unique ethnos-religious group possess identifiable identities. The identities manifests in physical appearance, religious practice, cultural belief and entrepreneurial engagements etc. A major distinctive characteristic common with the Jews all over the world is their intricate attraction to the state of Israel which they considered as their ancestral origin. With this in mind, even with full citizenship of the host country, they still do not divorce strong attachment to the state of Israel thus the ultimate goal of an average Jew is to protect and defend their ancestral home land.

According to Nehme (2000), "like their Christian and Muslim counterpart, the Jews are conservative and sometimes militant. Their zealotry and willingness to sacrifice for a cause provide them with an inordinate amount of power especially when it comes to matter affecting religion and Israel". In other word, by their nature the Jews have strong emotional attachment to matter of religion and Israel and are ready to defend

this cause using every available means at their disposal. Through religion and other collaborative engagement especially philanthropic activities, they project and protect the interest of what and where they believe is their ancestral home. This no doubt plays significant role in awakening the Jews consciousness. The Jewish consciousness is aggravated by the complexities of United States political, social and economic environment which appears to be immune to individual effort but rather penetrable easily to social cultural groups. The above assertion provides a foundational background and insight to the emergence of the powerful Jewish lobby in the United States. The Jews in diaspora, that is those Jews that domicile in Germany, Spain, Russian, and other part of Eastern Europe before the holocaust, on arrival in US do not waste time in settling down in local communities where they engaged in basic economic activities that provide income to support their much-cherished ethnic identities and assimilation into the American culture. In other word, having realize on arrival the complexities of the American society especially against the backdrop of the understanding that individual effort yields less result but collective action, the Jews began to come together to form loosed organizations and other interest grouping to agitate for furthering and protection of their interest. As a corollary to the above, Arnold (2018), averred that “the Jews have been bred and raised to be entrepreneurial for thousands of years. For instance, earlier in some part of Europe, they were barred from owning land, from trade guilds, and from certain white collar professions, all they could do was engaged in menial jobs such as money lending, and peddling and petty trading”. Arnold argued further that Jewish tradition always emphasized the importance of study, learning, and getting a good education. So, there was a bit of evolution whereby Jews ended up having a disproportionate number of their people good at businesses. Also, “since they were the last to be hired and the first to be fired due to inherent discrimination toward the Jewish race in Europe, they leaned towards being independent that meant owning their own businesses. In another corroborative argument, Arnold went further to assert that the discrimination and the pogrom against the Jews in Europe make them stronger and ever ready to take greater risk for self-survival. In other word, they are mostly immune to fear of failure and ready to pay supreme price in business decisions. They have seen it all and are not intimidated by any extenuating circumstances. From general economic analysis, risk taking is an acclaimed panacea to business successes.

The foregoing revealed in clear terms the fundamental reason underlying the Jews success in businesses and subsequent emergence as billionaires in the United States. Succinctly put, the business acumen coupled with the Jewish traditions that encourage education and learning contributed immensely to the rise to affluence of Jews in the United States. With huge financial muscles it is natural for Jewish to influence decisions and exercise dominance on the political space using the strategy of campaign financing.

In summary, having escaped from the peril of the holocaust and other harsh social political conditions in Europe to the United States, the Jews immediately engaged in profitable economic ventures such as trading, manufacturing and banking where necessary as means of livelihood. They also does not waste time in taking advantage of the open educational system in US to enrol in schools and veer into profession such as Law, Engineering, Banking, Medicine and Information and Communication Technology. In addition, the open and free social policies in the United States created conducive atmosphere for them to engage in commerce and other profitable economic activities without inhibitions. The ugly experience of the past also ignited some level of consciousness which underlies the belief that coming together to form interest group to fight for their interest and common share values is paramount thus, the need for strong and virile lobby organizations. Consequently, from small scale trading to manufacturing concern, banking to large scale corporate businesses, the Jews were elevated to position of affluence producing billionaire businessmen with huge financial resources to manipulate legislations and public opinions. They subsequently rose to position of authority in the United States playing major role in critical foreign policies decisions especially as it affect the Middle East. We can asserts from the above that the entrepreneurial skill of the Jews which they exhibited from the onset on arrival in the United States play critical role in their elevation to position of influence and affluences.

7. The Power of the Jewish Lobby Group in the United States

There is no doubt that the Jews Lobby organization exercise considerable power over United States Middle East foreign policy and other domestic affairs. The power can be aptly described as ‘soft power’ because it does not involve application of force but high wired politics, manoeuvring, collective bargaining and use of financial inducement through campaign financing. To a large extent, the Jewish Lobby organization have succeeded more than any other lobby groups in the United States in using this power to achieve desire objective which primarily is the advancement of the US-Israel relations. The Jews today now constitute considerable percentage of the billionaires in the United States. The Forbes magazine edition of America wealthiest individual in 2018 as reported in the Times of Israel (2020) revealed that five individuals of

Jewish descent make the list of the ten wealthiest people in the United States. Below table buttressed this assertion.

Table 1. Five richest Jews in the United States and their business organization.

S/N	Name	Net worth in billions	Business organization
1	Mark Zuckerberg	\$46.1 billion	Founder of Facebook
2	Larry Ellison	\$58.4 billion	Founder of Oracle
3	Larry Page	\$53.8 billion	Co-founder of Google
4	Sergery Brin	\$52.4 billion	Co-founder of Google
5	Michael Bloomberg	\$51.8 billion	Founder CEO of Bloomberg L.P.
Source: Times of Israel: https://www.timesofisrael.com/5-jews-make-forbes-list-of-top-10-wealthiest-americans retrieved June 2022			

The basic deduction from the above analysis is that 50% of the United States billionaires are Jews. From this we can draw a more general inference that the Jews are one of the richest races universally. It is clear from our previous analysis that Jews in the United States share common values these values are ethno-religious identity and strong affiliation with the states of Israel which they consider as their ancestral origin and desire to protect the security and territorial integrity of the country. It therefore not disputable that collective group where above named individuals are affiliated will pull huge financial resources to achieve desire interest at the expense of other with lean resources. Even in Nigeria or any other African society, it is a natural tendency that community with greater number of millionaires will be highly respected and often achieves their goals at the expense of the others. This factor undoubtedly explains the successes and unprecedented power and achievement of the powerful Jewish lobby group in the United States placing them in a position of being the highest donor in any campaign financing.

8. Jewish Lobby Organizations in the United States

There are numerous Jewish organizations in the United States each representing different interest but are unanimous in primary objective which ultimately is the protection and advancement of the interest of the state of Israel and that of Jewish people in the United States. Primarily, a significant goal of these organizations is to ensure US uninterrupted financial aids and support to Israel especially in fighting perceived adversaries, the neighbouring Arab countries. The Jewish organizations also sprang up to advance the interest of the Jews in the United States against the backdrop of the previous ugly experience in Europe. The devastating experience in Europe engenders close affinity among the Jews triggering spirit of oneness and belief in common share values. Also, the realization that their interest needs to be adequately protected to avoid repeat of the past ignite the desire to come together and speak with one voice through strong and virile interest group. The most popular and most active Jewish lobby organisations are the Conference of President of Major Jewish Organizations. This body represents the mouthpiece of the Jewish union; it articulates the position of the lobby groups and presents it to the executive arm of the United States government for considerations and concession.

Again, the America Israel Public Affairs Committee (AIPAC) is the most virile of the lobby group, they lobby the congress by positioning themselves at the corridor of the congress building to monitor the disposition of the congressmen on matters that concerns Israel. The focus is essentially the senators that benefited from the largesse of the Jewish lobby. In other word, senators who have received monetary donation and other support from the lobby group are often under the eagle eyes of the lobby group. The Evangelical organization like Christian United for Israel (CUFI) under the leadership of Pastor John Hagee also play active role in advancing the Jewish interest. The organisation adopts popular Christian eschatology to convince millions of Christians in the United States including decision makers and many part of the world to be sympathetic to Israel.

9. The Influence of the Jewish Lobby Group on the United States Middle East Foreign Policy

Earlier in this article we ascertained the fact that the Jewish lobby group plays significant role in shaping the United States Middle East foreign policy in favour of Israel. One of the reasons for their successes is the strategy of financing electioneering campaign of political candidate or parties. The strategy of campaign financing enabled the lobby group obtain policy concessions. Such concession includes among others strengthened the US-Israel relations, procuring annual \$3billion financial aid to Israel, military and technological assistance and most critically the diplomatic coverage of Israel at the United Nations. The achievement placed Israel on a pedestal where Israel unlike other countries ignore United Nations Security Council resolution 242 relating to evacuation from occupied Palestinian’s territory of Gaza and other

territories acquired in 1967 six days war without any punitive consequences. The Jewish lobby group manipulate United States on critical issues that impacted on the US Middle East strategic national interest, they lobbied to ensure serious economic sanctions on Iran for their nuclear program, restrict sales of Arm by the United States to the Arab countries, they have also pushed United States to go to war with Iraq and other perceived Israel adversaries. It should be noted that there are several lobby groups in the United States lobbying for one interest or the others. There are Arab lobby, Indian lobby, Mexican lobby, Black Caucus all strive to advance the interest of their members cum home countries. However, the Jewish lobby group demonstrated higher level of efficiency unrivalled by any other interest group.

The lobby group represents a major domestic determinant of the United States Middle East foreign policy. The opinion and position of the lobby group no doubt constitutes significant input parameter for the formulation and implementation of the US Middle East foreign policy and other domestic affairs. The Jews lobby group shaped through various strategies the US foreign policy direction in the Middle East making it entirely pro-Israel.

As stated earlier, the Jewish lobby group actively gets involved in the formulation, implementation as well as post implementation processes of the US foreign policy in the Middle East. They have become overwhelmingly effective in shaping the direction of the US Middle East foreign policy favorably toward Israel that even when Israel action negate the fundament ideology publicly professed by the United States, US have no alternative than to continue to provide support for Israel. In other word, when Israel action deviate and even diametrically opposed to the United States strategic interest, her support for Israel remains intact. The Jewish lobby group have been able to exercise commanding control over the US Middle East foreign policy in specific instances such as the case of the attack on the US Naval Ship-USS liberty 1 in 1967 by Israel, the Iranian nuclear deal, United States military financing to Israel, involvement in the US arms sales policy in the Middle East, support for Israel in its battle against Hamas and the diplomatic coverage of Israel at the UN Security Council.

The focal point of the tactics adopted by the Jewish lobby to influence the United States foreign policy is directed toward members of the United States Congress, the executive arm of government and their teaming members both Jews and non-Jews. The primary objective is to advance United States relationship with Israel galvanizing United States support for the states of Israel and also directing US opposition to those nations perceived as enemies of Israel. Any matter outside this is beyond the scope of the lobby group and are therefore accorded less attention.

The Jews lobby group understands the importance of the policy origination stage in foreign policy processes therefore determined the candidate who occupies political offices. This they do by actively involved in the electoral processes that produce public office holders at the congressional and presidential level. The Lobby groups leverage their huge financial advantage to provide fund in support of political campaign to particular candidate of interest mostly those candidates that share the vision of the lobby group as regard matters that concerns Israel. Candidate with critical view of Israel is declared persona non grata, opponent of such candidate is supported with adequate fund so that such candidate can be defeated in the election. In reality, most candidate with the backing and support of the lobby group are sure of electoral success while candidate opposed by the lobby group cannot be sure of electoral success rather defeat await them at the poll. The implication is that with the Jewish lobby position as major donor of campaign fund for political candidate, every political candidate courts the lobby group for donation and for electoral victory. In the United States, it is common for political candidate to publicly profess support for Israel and also express commitment to support policy favorable to the country, on the other hand, most candidate avoid like plaque making inflammatory statement that are critical of Israel to avoid the wrath of the lobby group.

According to Mearsheimer and Walt (2007), "No lobby group has managed to divert U.S. foreign policy as far from what the American national interest would otherwise suggest, while simultaneously convincing Americans that U.S. and Israeli interests are essentially identical". They argue further that "in its basic operations, the Jewish lobby is not different from other interest groups like the farm lobby, steel and textile workers, and other ethnic lobbies but what sets the Israel lobby apart is their extraordinary effectiveness. The loosed coalition that makes up the lobby group has significant leverage over the executive branch, as well as the ability to make sure that the lobby's perspective on Israel is widely reflected in the mainstream media. They also claim that the American Israel Public Affairs Committee (AIPAC) in particular has a stranglehold on the U.S. Congress, due to its ability to reward legislators and congressional candidates who support its agenda, and to punish those who challenge it. The statement above from Mearsheimer and Walt

the two most recognize authority on the subject matter demonstrated significantly the power of the Jewish lobby.

10. United States Diplomatic Coverage of Israel

Diplomatic coverage of Israel at the UN Security Council is one of the critical areas of success recorded by the Jewish lobby group. This involve preventing the UN from taking critical position on Israel or imposing sanctions on Israel as a result of Israel's activities in the Palestinians occupied territory. As earlier stated in this study, the Jewish lobby group overwhelming stronghold on the United States foreign policy asides shaping the United States Middle East foreign policy also has direct effect on the voting pattern of the United States at the UN Security Council. United States through the prodding of the Jewish lobby group provides diplomatic coverage for Israel by vetoing United Nation Security Council draft resolutions that are critical of Israel. In other word, the Jewish lobby leverages their influence and support from the US Congress and the executive arm to pre-determine the position of the United States on substantive issues concerning Israel and the Middle East at the UN. The diplomatic coverage by the United States granted Israel immunity against United Nation's Security Council resolutions. It should be noted that United States is one of the five permanent members of the Security Council, through its veto power, affirmative action by other permanent members could be vetoed by the United States thus halting the passage of such resolution and automatically made it null and voids. The United States has consistently utilized this power effectively to protect Israel thus given Israel and edged over other countries in the region. Some scholar's belief that United States have over the years used its Veto power to neutralize resolutions that are critical of Israel 43 times, other argued that this have been used 53 times since its inception. However, what is of critical importance to us in this study is that the United States protects Israel using the instrumentality of the Veto power. This fact was supported by Robel when he avers as follows; "the U.S-Israel relation is unique and also most talked about topic in the world. This is because it is said that, the U.S. is the ultimate protector of Israel in all cases. From the very beginning of the birth of Israel in Palestine to present time, the U.S. is working as the security provider to Israel. Since 1982, the U.S. vetoed 33 United Nations Security Council (UNSC) resolutions that were critical of Israel. Not only this, in 2014 the U.S. was the only country in the world that voted against the United Nations investigating human rights violations in Gaza unleashed by Israel's military assault in the name of "Operation Protective Edge." Why is the U.S. backing Israel in all cases despite continuous pressure from the international community (Robel, 2020:26). Robel concluded that he has studied many articles and found that the internal factors like Israeli lobby, is the key factors behind this backup. "The Israeli lobby within the U.S. have influential role on foreign policy making process. The lobby provided campaign fund to the political candidate so that they work in favor of Israeli. Robel argued further that the media, within the hand of Israeli ownership, broadcast those news and programs which help to manipulate the U.S. citizens".

In the same manner Staff (2017), opined that the United States vetoed a draft UN Security Council resolution on Monday that rejected President Donald Trump's move to recognize Jerusalem as Israel's capital, marking the 43rd time the US has used its veto power against Israel-related UN Security Council draft resolutions. The position of United States on the UN draft resolutions that are critical of Israel demonstrated the level of involvement by the Jewish lobby group in the US foreign policy. The lobby group especially AIPAC consistently mount pressure on the congress and the executive arm of the United States government to kill resolutions that are not favorable to Israel. Even when the Israel actions are at variance with United States strategic interest and professed ideology, the Jewish lobby group prods the US to take such action to protect the state of Israel.

It should be noted that the only time in over 40 years that United States allows UN resolution on Israel was in 2016 during the tail end of Obama administration. The resolution 2334, which called for an end to the Israel settlement on the Palestinians occupied territories, sailed through. US simply abstain from voting instead of Vetoing the resolution thus allow it passed by 14-0 margin. However, the decision of the United States was attended with outrage and condemnation by the Jewish lobby and other Zionist evangelical organization and their supporters who promised to allies with the oncoming Donald Trump administration to negate the resolution. The lobby group subsequently got the support of Donald Trump who took drastic measures to consolidate Israel's gains on the occupied territories. Trump recognized Jerusalem as the capital of Israel and subsequent move United States embassy from Tel Aviv to Jerusalem.

11. Strategies Adopted by the Jewish Lobby Group to Influence the United States Middle East Foreign Policy

Earlier in this study we ascertained the fact that the Jewish lobby group plays significant role in shaping the United States Middle East foreign policy in favour of Israel. We demonstrated the lobby group effectiveness

by bringing to fore some favors successfully accrued to Israel by the group. Such favour includes among others strengthened the US-Israel relations, procuring annual \$3billion financial aid to Israel, military and technological assistance and most critically the diplomatic coverage of Israel at the United Nations. This for instance enables Israel unlike other countries ignore United Nations resolution 242 relating to evacuation from occupied Palestinian's territory of Gaza and other territories acquired in the 1967 six days war such as the Golan Height and South Lebanon without any punitive consequences. The Jewish lobby groups manipulate United States on critical issues that impacted on the US Middle East strategic national interest, they lobbied to ensure serious economic sanctions on Iran for their nuclear program, restrict sales of arm to the Arab countries. It should be noted that there are several lobby groups in the United States lobbying for one interest or the others. However, the Jewish lobby group demonstrated higher level of efficiency unrivalled by any other interest group in the US. Some scholars attributed this to will power and effectiveness.

The critical concern here is how the Jews emerged from the ashes of deprivation, neglect and holocaust in Europe to become major influence on the United States Middle East foreign policy and other domestic affairs. We are concern about what put them at such vantage position to influence the US Middle East foreign policy. The Jewish historical experience which includes discrimination, deprivation and attempted extermination in Europe provide the spring board to emergence as power brokers in the United States. The engagement in self-businesses turns out to be the vehicle that lifted them to the billionaire's club in comparism with other ethno-religion groups. Naturally, economic power comes with political influences. Realizing the economic advantage they possess, the Jews begging to form loosed coalition to advance their interest in the United States and that of Israel considered as their ancestral origin. The complexities of the United States social political milieu which recognizes group effort at the expense of individual efforts paved way for interest group to thrive significantly. Thus, the Jews in the United States key into this space, came together to established varying loose organizations to lobby for their interest.

At this junction we are compelled to interrogate the strategies adopted by the Jewish lobby group to influence the United States Middle East foreign policy and other domestic matters and why are they are so successful. As stated earlier, the Jewish lobby group exerts commanding control on the United States Middle East foreign policy. The effectiveness of the group in goal attainment has become a source of concern not only to the world but other rival lobby groups in the United States such as the Arab lobby which are less popular and less impactful. The basic fundamental question arising from these concerns is how the Jewish lobby group achieved the successes recorded so far and what specific strategies adopted to achieve these feats. One thing is to have economic advantage another is to be efficient in using this advantage to advance ones interest. The Jewish lobby group demonstrated in clear terms ability to combine economic advantage with determination and will power to gain social political relevance. There is no doubt that the Jews lobby group in pursuant of their mission of protecting the state of Israel adopt varying strategies to influence the congress and the executive arm of the United States government for favorable legislative and policy outcome. The strategies are designed in response to the peculiar social political environment in the United States. The strategies ranges from campaign donations, bloc voting, ownership and control of Think Tanks organizations, college campus student activisms, mass media and motion picture propaganda, charges of anti-semitism, lobbying to evangelism. Since policy decision procedurally emanates from the executive and the legislative arm of the government, these arms of government are the target of the lobby group. The Jews lobby group understands perfectly the significant of the two arms of government in the achievement of their overall objective then direct effort not only to the individual occupying the positions but directly at the recruitment and selection processes into those positions. Naturally from experience even in African politics, there is a reciprocal relationship between loyalty and commitment of political office holders and their sponsors. To this extent, the Jewish lobby group play active role in donating campaign fund to prefer political candidate to subsidize campaign logistics and other cost of elections in return for policy concession.

12. Political Campaign Finance

Political campaign finance or donation is a veritable tool used by the Jewish lobby group to secure commitment and loyalty of members of congress and the executive. The strategy is to provide campaign funds for candidate seeking political office with favorable disposition towards Israel to enable them win and also provide fund for opponent of candidate with critical view of Israel in other to defeat such candidate in the poll. According to Bard (1988), "political campaign contributions are also considered an important means of influence, political campaign donations, refers to the funds raised to promote candidates, political parties, or policy initiatives. It refers to the funds received by political parties from private sources for general electoral, administrative and logistic purposes. Political campaigns involve considerable cost,

including travel costs of candidates and staff, accommodation, political consulting, advertising and other logistics. Bard argued further that, "campaign spending depends on the region for instance, in the United States, television advertising time must be purchased by the campaigns, and some campaign rally venue must be paid for. He warn that the need to raise money to maintain expensive political campaigns have negative impact on representative democracy because of the influence those who donate large sum of money have on politicians.

According to Pastine and Pastine (2013), "although the political science literatures indicates that most contributors give to support parties or candidates with whom they are already in agreement, there is wide public perception which of cause is the reality that donors expect government favors in return (such as specific legislation being enacted or defeated), so some scholars have come to view campaign finance with political corruption and bribery because funds are given to candidate in anticipation of support, loyalty and commitment."

AIPAC is at the vanguard of formal Jewish lobby in the US congress, it is the channel through which campaign donation are deliver to the preferred candidate. However, AIPAC in the real sense does not give donations directly to candidates, but those who donate to AIPAC are often important political contributors. In addition, AIPAC only helps to connect donors with candidates, especially to the network of pro-Israel Political Action Committees. AIPAC president Howard Friedman said in April 2020, that "AIPAC meets with every candidate running for congress; these candidates receive in-depth briefings to help them completely understand the complexities of Israel's predicament and that of the Middle East as a whole. They often ask each candidate to write a 'position paper' on their views of the US-Israel relationship so it can be cleared where they stand on the subject." The process of political campaign donation has become more structure and stringent than before, the Jewish lobby group provide campaign donation to support candidate with soft disposition toward Israel and also starve and oppose candidate with critical outlook on Israel. In other word, campaign donations are given out conditionally, one of the conditions is favorable disposition toward Israel. As a candidate, you must be ready to defend Israel cause to access the fund. Those candidates with favorable disposition toward Israel not only on paper but by conduct are handsomely rewarded.

To Bard (1988), "politicians considered too critical of Israel who AIPAC has helped to defeat include the following amongst several others: Cynthia McKinney, Paul Findley, Earl F. Hilliard, Pete McCloskey, Senators William Fulbright and Roger Jepsen, and Adlai Stevenson III in his campaign for governor of Illinois in 1982. The defeat of Charles H. Percy, who was the Senator for Illinois until 1985, has been attributed to AIPAC-coordinated donations to his opponent because he supported the sale of AWACS military planes to Saudi Arabia. The Donations included \$1.1 million released for anti-Percy advertising by Michael Goland, who was also a major contributor to AIPAC and a staunch member of the Jewish lobby group. Campaign donation strategy is not in any way peculiar to United States political environment; it revealed generally the significant of the role of patronage function in politics. The patronage function emphasizes reward system for supports and loyalty. Candidates supported with campaign funds to win election are mostly likely to reward their benefactors with legislative or policy concessions. The Jewish lobby groups leverage these principles and take advantage of it to achieve desire results when the opportunity presented itself.

This position was buttresses by Ben-Zion (2012) when he said "big-dollar donors can have big influence. They are often invited to state dinners at the White House and other events with the president. They also may be asked to weigh in on public policy, especially if it affects their financial interest, the ranks of ambassadors, advisory panels, and other government jobs traditionally are filled with those who have been generous during the campaign". Amri (2013), also emphasized the importance of campaign donation as major strategy adopted by the Jewish lobby group to influence US foreign policy decisions when he opined that, "the Jewish lobby group adopted various strategies to gain the congress support. These strategies range from organizing coalition, lobbying, grassroots techniques and the campaign donation". He asserted further that "among these techniques, campaign support is one of the techniques that could directly explain the special relationship between the lobby group and the US congress and the executive arm of the government". The Washington lobby (1987) described the role of campaign donation to the effectiveness of the Jewish lobby activities. They averred that campaign contribution to members of congress serve two important functions to lobbying organizations. Political support not only can indulge a congressional man to back the group legislative interest but also can help to ensure that members friendly to the group goal remain in office. This perspective was shared by Mearsheimer and Walt (2007), when they asserted that "American Israel Public Affair Committee (AIPAC)'s success in pushing through its agenda is due largely to its ability to reward legislators and congressional candidates who support its agenda, and to punish decisively those who

challenge it. Money is critical to U.S. election and AIPAC makes sure that its friends get strong financial support from the myriad of pro-Israel Political Action Committees (PAC). Those seen as hostile to Israel, on the other hand, can be sure that AIPAC will direct campaign contributions to their political opponents. AIPAC also organizes letter-writing campaigns and encourages newspaper editors to endorse pro-Israel candidates (Mearsheimer and Walt, 2007).

Speaking about pro-Israel lobby group in America and their tactics Arke (2009), claimed that J Streets Political Action Committee and AIPAC plays significant role as the highest donor to political candidate and congressional members in 2018. According to him, "one of the most powerful international issue lobbies is that of the pro-Israel crowd. Well-financed and politically powerful, the pro-Israel lobby is a major force on American foreign affairs that looks to continue America's military and fiscal support of the Jewish nation-state. As a corollary to the above, Ben-Zion (2012) also revealed that, in the 2012 United States presidential election, the biggest donor to Mitt Romney's presidential campaign, and the two biggest donors to Barack Obama's reelection bid are all Jewish. He posited further that "the largest declared donor overall is casino mogul Sheldon Adelson, who is worth an estimated \$25 billion. He donated \$34.2 million so far to aid Romney and organizations supporting the Republican challenger to Obama reelection bid. In the same vein, President Obama's top two donors are Jeffrey Katzenberg who donated \$2.566 million and Irwin Jacobs who donated \$2.122 million respectively".

Summarily, the above analysis provided in details the relationship between campaign donation and effective lobbying in the United States. The Jewish lobby interest groups mostly apply this strategy to gain influence both on the congress and the executive branch of the United States government. As stated earlier, it is a reciprocal gesture where the beneficiary of campaign donation in turn recognizes the benefactor by way of loyalty, commitment, advancement of those interest represented by the benefactors. We can therefore simply infer that the Jewish lobby unprecedented achievement in influencing the United States Middle East foreign policy both at the congressional and executive level is due largely to the campaign donation strategy.

13. The Jewish Voting Power

Another major strategy adopted by the Jewish interest group to shape the United States Middle East foreign policy is voting power. This could be explained in terms of bloc voting or simply the swayable voting pattern of the Jews. This strategy work effectively at the recruitment and selection processes of political candidate and at the level of political education and socializations. The peculiarity of the United States electoral system gave the Jews the requisite voting power which is exercise on the election of electors to the Electoral College who in turn elect the president. The Jews lobby groups leverage their numeric strength in states with the highest number of electors to influence the election of president.

The key role played by the Jews in securing electoral victory for politicians in the United States was confirmed by Bard (2009) when he asserted that, "the Jews have devoted themselves to politics with almost religious fervor. Jews have the highest percentage voters' turnout of any ethnic group and that of the American Jewish population roughly, 94% live in thirteen key Electoral College states which alone are worth enough electoral votes to elect the president. If you add the non-Jews shown by opinion polls to be as pro-Israel as Jews, it is clear Israel has the support of one of the largest veto groups in the country". Bard goes on to say that for United States congressmen "there are no benefits to candidates taking an openly anti-Israel stance when looking at the costs in term of both loss of campaign contributions and votes from Jews and non-Jews alike who are supporters of the Jew." The Most important fact about the Jewish vote in America, according to Helmreich (2001) lies in the fact that it is a uniquely swayable in bloc.... "The issue of support for Israel by a candidate has proven capable of spurring a sizable portion of Jews to switch parties in large enough numbers to tip the scales in national or statewide elections. Moreover, the Israel swing vote is especially open to political courtship because, unlike the interests of other minority groups, support for Israel has long been compatible with traditional Republican and Democratic agendas. On the other hand, being distinctively unsupportive of Israel can significantly hurt a candidate's chances.

From the Encyclopedia Britannica retrieved in June 2022, top 4 states with the largest Jewish populations account for 127 electoral votes, top 10 states with the largest Jewish populations account for 244 electoral votes, 270 electoral votes are needed to secure the White House. The import of the above analysis is that Jewish have the highest number of voters turn out in any election compare to any other ethnic group in the United States aside this, Jews votes are swayable in bloc. This is significant politically; it put the Jews at a relatively comparative advantage within the Electoral College system. Political candidate intending to win election must naturally display open support for the Jewish lobby cause so as to obtain support from

majority of the Jews within the Electoral College states. The Jews lobby group capitalized on this to obtain commitment and loyalty from candidate in an election and even incumbent seeking for re-election. We have identified earlier that the Jewish lobby is a one issue base lobby, this issue is Israel. Most politicians in US align with the interest of the Jewish lobby to win election or retain position. The Middle East foreign policy is no exception in this regard. This implies that aside campaign donations, swayable bloc voting system is a potent tool the Jewish lobby group used to secure loyalty of the congress and the executive arms of the US government.

Aside the above strategies, the Jewish lobby group also adopt the following strategies to influence the United States Middle East foreign policy in favour of Israel;

- ✓ Influence on think thank organization,
- ✓ Media and motion picture propaganda,
- ✓ Education of politicians and sponsored trip to Israel,
- ✓ Grooming of pro-Israel student activism on college campuses,
- ✓ AIPAC annual policy conference,
- ✓ Frequent accusation of anti-semitism.

The resultant effect is clearly manifested in the ease and seamless way the Jewish lobby as an interest group influence the US Middle East foreign policy making it entire pro-Israel.

14. Conclusion

From the foregoing, we concluded that interest group play critical role in foreign policy formulation and implementation. They are an integral part of the input parameters requires for foreign policy decisions. Against the back drop of the success recorded by the powerful Jewish lobby group especially in making the US Middle East foreign policy entirely pro-Israel, we infer that foreign policy is a reflection of group interest. In every social political and economic system, there are various interest groups with shared interest seeking to influence government policy to advance this interest. However, we find out that output from foreign policy decisions mostly reflects the interest of the dominant interest group, the Jewish lobby group is a dominant interest group in the United States.

The US Middle East foreign policy is entire pro-Israel because the powerful Jewish lobby group represent dominant interest that prod the US foreign policy decision makers to formulate and implement policies in favour of Israel and the Jews in the United States as a whole. In other word, there is a nexus between United States Middle East foreign policy and the powerful Jewish lobby group. The pro-Israel United States foreign policy posture is structurally and architecturally designed by the powerful Jewish lobby group. The special relationship that exists between Israel and the United States is obviously triggered and engineered by the powerful Jewish lobby group contrary to the widely spread claim of historical homogeneity, similarity in democracy, religion, cultural and common share values.

One of the strategies adopted by interest group in the United States to influence policy decision is lobbying. They most often lobby government for favorable policy output. The powerful Jewish lobby group adopted various strategies ranging from, campaign donation, bloc voting system, influence on think thank organization, media and social media propaganda, education of politician, campus student activism to frequent charges of anti-semitism against those with critical view of Israel. These strategies have been very effective considering the level of successes recorded by the Jewish lobby group in shaping the US Middle East foreign policy in a pro-Israel direction.

Also, interest group albeit private in posture and objective, they play active role in political recruitment. The powerful Jewish lobby group is actively involved in the recruitment of candidate into the congress and the executive arm of government. They often provide financial support for political candidate with positive disposition toward their cause and oppose candidate with critical view as part of the lobby processes. This strategy work well in onboarding prefer candidate into the political system. The overall goal is to obtain policy concession in favour of member and cause represented.

15. Recommendations

Bases on the foregoing analysis, we recommend a robust framework for management of interest group. We identify that, interest group are integral part of any political system and cannot be isolated, activities of interest group should be streamlined in such a way as not to allow interest group, dominate, dictate and shape direction of government policy as observed in the case of the Jewish lobby group. The Jewish lobby

group practically exercises commanding control over the US Middle East foreign policy making it completely pro-Israel. This fact is at the root of major resentment, tension and violent in the region.

The social, political and economic environment in the US should be re-engineered to reduce the overwhelming dominance of interest group. Individual opinion and voice should be heard and recognized to pave way for level playing ground and government policies based on objectivity.

The US government should device a framework regulating electioneering campaign to make it less expensive. This will reduce drastically reliance on private campaign finance thus given the interest group less opportunity to use campaign finance as instrument to pin down member of congress and the executive arm for policy concession. This will allow a more robust and objective policy from government decision free from group interest.

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